

CHEMICAL AND NUTRITIONAL EVALUATION OF THE RAW SEEDS OF MACROTYLOMA CHRYSANTHUM

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents chemical and nutritional information on the underutilised seeds of *M. chrysanthum*. Chemical analyses show that the seeds are not rich in lipids and hence have a low energy value. The seeds were found to be rich in some essential amino acids (especially lysine), macroelements (Na, K, Mg) and ascorbic acid. The antinutrient levels of tannin, phytic acid and hydrogen cyanide were found to be low hence the seeds could be considered to be nutritionally good.

KEYWORDS: Amino acids, Lipids, Macrotyloma chrysanthum, Mineral elements, Proteins, Proximate composition.

INTRODUCTION

A reasonable percentage of the population of developing countries suffers from protein malnutrition arising from inadequate intake. In Nigeria today, there is an increase in the monthly earnings of workers but there is also an unprecedented increase in the prices of common food substances such that adequate protein supply is still a serious problem to the citizenry. Although there is an acute need to meet daily nutritional requirements, available rich and cheap sources of nutrients are either unexplored or were abandoned with the advent of modernity and civilization. For sometime now efforts have been directed at identifying alternative and cheap sources of protein (Enobong and Carnovali, 1992, Udoh *et al.*, 1995a, b; Udoh and Akpan, 1997).

Macrotyloma chrysanthum (A. Chev.) Verdc. is a leguminous plant whose seeds were widely consumed in Eastern Nigeria up to the late sixties. The cooked seeds of this plant were eaten with cooked or roasted plantain, cocoyam, yam, water yam and the three leaved yam. However, with the increasing cultivation of various varieties of cowpea, this food has been neglected. It's cultivation is not given priority and is almost extinct in some areas.

In the present study, an attempt is made to decipher the chemical composition of the seeds of *M. chrysanthum* and to understand its nutrient potential.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mature dry pods of *M. chrysanthum* were collected from a local farm at Ukana Ikot Ideh, Essien Udim Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The seeds were separated from the pods and dried in an oven at the temperature of 50⁰C for 24 hours. The seeds were then pulverized into fine powder using a clean and dry electric blender. The powder obtained was stored in an air tight plastic container and used for analyses.

Moisture content was determined by drying 40 transversely cut seeds in an oven at 60⁰C and the value expressed as a percentage. Crude protein content was calculated by multiplying the percentage Kjeldahl nitrogen (Humpries, 1956) by a factor of 6.25. Crude lipid, crude fibre and the ash contents were analysed by the (AOAC, 2000) methods. The nitrogen free extract (NFE) or total crude carbohydrate was obtained

by difference. The energy content of the seeds was estimated in kJ by multiplying the percentages of crude protein, crude fat and NFE by factors of 16.7, 37.7 and 16.7 respectively and taking the sum of the products.

TABLE 1. PROXIMATE, MINERAL AND ANTINUTRIENT COMPOSITION OF THE SEED OF *M. chrysanthum*

Proximate Values, g/100g	
Moisture (wet weight)	15.80 ± 0.02
Crude fibre	9.30 ± 0.42
Crude protein	23.19 ± 0.01
Crude fat	2.70 ± 0.04
Ash	5.53 ± 0.02
Carbohydrate	59.28
Calorific value kJ/100g	1479.04
Mineral composition, mg/100g	
Sodium	6055.57 ± 27.49
Potassium	990.00 ± 0.41
Calcium	76.67 ± 0.59
Magnesium	2571.67 ± 23.45
Zinc	35.55 ± 1.25
Copper	1.18 ± 0.14
Iron	26.28 ± 0.02
Manganese	3.75 ± 0.10
Cobalt	0.07 ± 0.01
Cadmium	ND
Chromium	ND
Antinutrients, mg/100g	
HCN	1.19 ± 0.03
Oxalate	8.36 ± 0.11
Phytic acid	8.70 ± 0.01
Tannins	1.55 ± 0.10
Vitamins, mg/100g	
Ascorbic acid	94.65 ± 0.50

*Each value represent the mean ± SD for triplicate determinations

A known mass of the dry powdered sample was ashed at 600°C in a muffle furnace for 4 hours. The ash was dissolved in 6M HCl, made to a definite volume and used for mineral analysis. Sodium and potassium were determined with a flame photometer (Jenway PF 7 Flame photometer, Essex, UK) while other mineral elements were determined using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Unicam Analytical System, Model 919, Cambridge, UK).

Total oxalate was determined by the method of Dye (1956). Hydrocyanic acid was estimated by the alkaline titration method (AOAC, 2000). The colorimetric method of (Burns, 1971) was used for the determination of tannic acid while phytic acid was estimated with the method of (Wheeler and Ferrel, 1971). Vitamin C was determined by the indophenol reduction method (AOAC, 2000).

Amino acids were determined with an automatic amino acid analyzer using the principles of (Moore, 1963) and (Spackman *et al.*, 1958). The total (true) proteins were extracted by the method of Basha *et al.* (1976). However, ethanol treatment was omitted in order to save the prolamin fraction. The extracted proteins were

purified by precipitation with cold 20% trichloroacetic acid (TCA) and estimated by the method of (Lowry *et al.*, 1951).

The methods of AOAC (2000) were used in the determination of acid value, saponification value, iodine number, peroxide value, ester value, % free fatty acid and unsaponifiable matter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data on proximate composition of *M. chrysanthum* seeds are shown in Table 1. The seeds contain higher amounts of moisture than the 10% obtained for cowpea and pigeon pea (Sinha, 1977) and 5.16% obtained for the seeds of *X. xylocarpa* (Siddhuraju *et al.*, 1995). The crude protein content is comparable to

TABLE 2. AMINO ACID COMPOSITION OF *M. chrysanthum* SEEDS.

Amino acid	<i>M. chrysanthum</i>	Whole Hen's egg (Paul <i>et al.</i> , 1976)	Amino Acid score on Paul <i>et al.</i> , 1976)
Isoleucine	5.2	5.6	92.86
Leucine	3.6	8.3	43.37
Lysine	7.7	6.2	124.19
Methionine	1.0	3.2	31.25
Cystine	0.3	1.8	16.67
Phenylalanine	4.8	5.1	94.12
Tyrosine	0.5	4.0	12.50
Threonine	4.1	5.1	80.39
Tryptophan	ND	1.8	-
Valine	4.0	7.5	53.30
Arginine	7.6	6.1	1.24
Histidine	3.4	2.4	1.41
Alanine	2.9	5.4	0.53
Aspartic acid	8.6	10.7	0.80
Glutamic acid	17.6	12.0	1.46
Glycine	1.1	3.0	0.36
Praline	2.9	3.8	0.76
Serine	4.4	7.9	0.55

values obtained for the seeds of the more common legumes while the contents of fat, fibre and ash were slightly higher than values reported for the seeds of other commonly cultivated legumes (Sinha, 1977).

Mineral analysis (Table 1) revealed that the levels of Zn, Fe and Mn were higher than their contents in some of the commonly cultivated legumes (Sinha, 1977; Siddhuraju *et al.*, 1995). The seeds of *M. chrysanthum* are, however, rich source of Na, K and Mg.

Although food legumes are important sources of dietary protein in developing countries, their acceptability and utilization is limited by the presence of relatively high concentrations of some anti-nutritional factors (Nowacki, 1980). Some of these antinutrients like cyanides and tannins are heat labile (Liener, 1980) whereas toxic amino acids, cyanogenic glucosides, saponins, flavones, isoflavones and alkaloids are heat stable (Nowacki, 1980). The data on the antinutrient levels in *M. chrysanthum* seeds are included in Table 1. The level of tannin appears to be low compared with other cultivated legumes such as green grain, cowpea, pigeon pea, black grain and *X. xylocarpa* (Khan *et al.*, 1979; Rao and Deosthale, 1982; Siddhuraju *et al.*, 1995). The amount of tannin in *M. chrysanthum* seed is, however, higher than that found in lima beans, 0.59 mg/100g (Egbe and Akinyele, 1990) but less than that in horse eye bean, 82 mg/100g (Osaniyi and Eka, 1978). The presence of tannins in foods even at low level, is undesirable from nutritional point of view. Tannins are known to inhibit the activities of digestive enzymes (Jambunathan and Smith, 1981).

Soaking and cooking are reported to reduce the levels of phenols, cyanides and tannins in foods (Sathe and Salunke, 1984). This may not apply in the case of *M. chrysanthum* because the seeds are not usually soaked before cooking and even after cooking the water is not usually discarded. The phytic acid content of *M. chrysanthum* is also very low compared with the value of 361 mg/100g in the seeds *X. xylocarpa* (Siddhuraju *et al.*, 1995); 135.8 mg/100g in the seeds of *V. unguiculata* and 13.5 mg/100g in bambara groundnut (Chakraborty and Eka, 1978). Phytate is known to lower the availability of essential mineral elements from food (Reddy *et al.*, 1982). The seeds of *M. chrysanthum* contain a low amount of oxalate when compared to the value of 43.0 mg/100g for soyabean seeds (Eka, 1977) and 42.2 mg/100g for the seeds of cowpea (Aremu, 1989). The present study also reveals the presence of HCN in the seeds of *M.*

TABLE 3. CONTENT OF TOTAL (TRUE) PROTEIN AND PROTEIN FRACTIONS OF *M. chrysanthum* SEEDS.

Protein fraction	g/100g seed flour*	g/100g seed protein
Total (true) protein	9.60 ± 0.42	100.00
Albumins	0.40 ± 0.27	4.17
Globulins	6.20 ± 0.05	64.58
Prolamins	0.10 ± 0.02	1.04
Glutelins	2.90 ± 0.08	30.21

* Values represent the mean ± SD for triplicate determinations

chrysanthum. However, the observed level of HCN is much lower than those found in safe varieties of pigeon pea, 86.19 mg/100g; soyabean, 71.81 mg/100g; locust bean, 26.46 mg/100g; bambara nuts, 88.24 mg/100g (Chakraborty and Eka, 1978) and *X. xylocarpa* seeds, 1.65 mg/100g (Siddhuraju *et al.*, 1995) and may not pose health problems.

The ascorbic acid content of *M. chrysanthum* seeds (94.65 mg/100g) was found to be higher than that of bambara nuts, 1.0 mg/100g (Hepper, 1970) and raw groundnut seeds – 5.8 mg/100g (Elegbede, 1998). Hence, the seeds of *M. chrysanthum* could be classified as a rich source of ascorbic acid.

The amino acid profile of the total seed proteins and the amino acid score are presented in Table 2. The data reveal that the sulphur containing amino acids, methionine and cysteine are the limiting amino acids. As a source of amino acids the seeds of *M. chrysanthum* are generally poorer than whole hen's egg (Paul *et al.*, 1976). However, with respect to the contents of isoleucine and lysine, the seeds are quite comparable to whole hen's egg. It is also noteworthy that the levels of isoleucine, lysine, phenylalanine and threonine obtained in this study compare favourably with those obtained for the seeds of *S. stenocarpa* (Nwokolo, 1987). Generally, the seeds of *M. chrysanthum* can be regarded as a moderate source of amino acids and need to be supplemented with other protein rich foods.

Seed protein fractionation of *M. chrysanthum* (Table 3) shows that the globulins and glutelins together constitute the bulk of seed protein (94.8%) as is the case with many other legumes (Boulter and Derbyshire, 1976; Rajaram and Janardhanan, 1991; Siddhuraju *et al.*, 1995). The percentage distribution of the globulin fraction obtained in this study is higher than the value of 54.8% reported for the seed protein of *X. xylocarpa* (Siddhuraju *et al.*, 1995). The ratio of albumin to globulin is, however, lower than that of *X. xylocarpa* (Siddhuraju *et al.*, 1995).

Data on the chemical characteristics of the crude lipid of *M. chrysanthum* seeds are shown in Table 4. The iodine value of oil is low and this is an indication of the low degree of unsaturation of the fatty acids present in the oil (Etuk, 2000). However, the iodine value of *M. chrysanthum* is comparable to that of palm oil which ranges between 37 to 57. Since the iodine value of the seed oil from *M. chrysanthum* is low, the oil can be classified as a non-drying oil (Ihekoronye and Ngoddy, 1985).

The saponification value gives an estimate of the mean molecular weight of the fatty acids present in the crude lipid. The value obtained in the present study is lower than those of commonly cultivated oil seeds such as groundnut and cotton seed (195) and guar meal (205) (Singh and Misra, 1981).

The acid value of *M. chrysanthum* seed oil is high compared with the reported values for other edible oils such as groundnut oil – 2.0; guar meal – 3.0; and cotton seed oil – 0.5 (Singh and Misra, 1981). The ester value of an oil gives some insight into the total glycerides present whereas the level of free fatty acids indicate the quality of an oil; the higher the amount of free fatty acid the lower the quality of the oil (Etuk, 2000).

The peroxide value of an oil is an index of the degree of peroxidation of the oil. The peroxide value obtained is high. This lipid oxidation and its resultant flavour impairment seriously limits the storage potential of the seed oil of *M. chrysanthum*.

TABLE 4. CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE OIL OF *M. chrysanthum* SEEDS.

Parameter	Content*
Acid value	19.35 ± 0.28
Saponification value	109.40 ± 0.00
Iodine value	45.30 ± 0.13
Ester value	90.05 ± 0.28
Peroxide value	83.33 ± 3.30
% Free fatty acid	9.73 ± 0.14
% Unsaponifiable yield	5.80 ± 0.10
Unsaponifiable matter	49.54 ± 0.40

* Values represent the mean ± SD for triplicate determinations

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the present study has shown that the seeds of *M. chrysanthum* are rich in critical nutrients. It's nutrient potential compares favourably with those of the more commonly consumed legumes. The antinutrient levels of tannin, oxalate, hydrogen cyanide and phytic acid in these seeds are reasonably low. There is, therefore, the need to revisit the consumption of these seeds in the absence of the better known food legumes.

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